

THE ECLECTIC APPROACH IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Karshibaev Khumoyun

An English teacher at school in Zarbdor, Jizzakh

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6416596>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st March 2022

Accepted: 10th March 2022

Online: 14th March 2022

KEY WORDS

method, approach,
eclectic approach, foreign
language, methodologies,
teaching, tactics,
strategies

ABSTRACT

In general, teaching is a noble profession in which children are educated at the elementary and secondary levels, and students are educated at the higher levels of colleges and universities. Learning is a process in which pupils learn a variety of skills in order to improve their physical, mental, and moral well-being. At every level, teachers employ a variety of methods, approaches, strategies, and techniques to teach their students. Teachers in English language classes use certain methods, approaches, and tactics while teaching a second or foreign language, notably English. Various teaching methods and approaches are developed via continuous review and observation. Grammar Translation, Direct Method, Audio-Lingual Method, and Communicative Language Teaching Approach (CLT) are among the most popular, and teachers use a variety of approaches and tactics to make English language learning flexible and appealing. Despite the fact that these strategies, approaches, and tactics are used by teachers in EL classrooms, there is still a gap between teacher and student. There has been a growing desire for a unified approach to language instruction throughout the years. The Eclectic approach is the possible solution, and it is a way for teaching English that blends diverse methods and methodologies. This method is dependent on the lesson's goals and the learners' skills. This research paper examines the benefits and drawbacks of the Eclectic method in the teaching of English as a foreign language. This article also looks at several components of the Eclectic method and how they might benefit English language teachers.

Without a question, English is the language through which much of the world's information is communicated. Science and technology, tourism, aviation, advertisements, education, journalism, entertainment, business and commerce, international relations, and other fields use

English extensively. English is taught as a second language and a foreign language in schools, colleges, and universities all over the world. English is taught at school, college, and university levels in Arab countries, China, Japan, Russia, and Brazil. Today, English is in high demand. Recently

English Language Teaching (ELT) has become one of the most rapidly growing industries around the globe. In fact, millions of students throughout the world are acquiring English language skills in order to pursue further education and get a job. The United Kingdom and the United States are playing a great role in promoting English language teaching both at home and overseas. The primary focus of this paper is on ELT and how instructors use certain methods, approaches, and strategies in EL classrooms, as well as the eclectic approach, which is often recognized as the most effective way for teaching English.

So far language teachers have used a variety of methods, approaches, and techniques, and they continue to do so. They are the Grammar-Translation Method, the Direct Method, the Audio-Lingual Method, Communicative Language Teaching, Silent Way, Suggestopedia, the Lexical Method, Cognitive Approach, Task-Based Language Learning, and so on are some of them. However, they may not be able to effectively teach the language using just one method, approach, or technique. This leads to the quest for a single or unifying strategy that incorporates all methods, approaches, and strategies and uses them contextually to help learners learn a foreign or second language more efficiently. The Eclectic Approach demonstrates that there is a unified approach to language acquisition that is flexible and adaptive.

The Eclectic Approach. Due to the communication revolution, everyone throughout the world need to adopt and acquire a global language in order to connect with other governments, regions, and nations. In today's society, English has

achieved global stature and is extensively utilized all over the world. English is also taught as a foreign and second language in schools, colleges, and universities all around the world. Teachers in ELT have used a variety of methods, approaches, and tactics, but they have been successful in educating students to improve their English communication abilities to some level. Therefore, a unique methodology that integrates all existing methods, approaches, and strategies in order to make English language learning more adaptable for students or learners from all cultures and backgrounds is required. In the final stage, the Eclectic Approach has been promoted in ELT.

The major goal is to build a new method that combines all of the existing approaches and incorporates them into ELT while maximizing the benefits of each method, strategy, and methodology. As a matter of fact, depending on the classroom situation, the fundamental concept is to apply all possible methods, approaches, and strategies in varied proportions. The Eclectic Approach is one that incorporates all language-teaching strategies based on the classroom situation and the abilities of learners.

The Eclectic Approach was advocated as almost all the individual methods had their strengths and weaknesses and not even a single method was responsible to the real and dynamic classroom context. Taking the drawbacks of the various methods into consideration, Brown (2002) argues that eclecticism finds the right solution as this approach permits the teacher to select what works well in their classrooms within their own dynamic contexts. Even Gilliland, James and Bowman (1994) declared that the

justification to adopt the Eclectic Approach lies in the single method or approach because a single method or approach has a narrow theoretical basis and has a fixed set of activities and hence it is inflexible.

Eclecticism is a philosophical approach that does not adhere to a single paradigm or set of assumptions, but instead draws from a variety of theories, styles, or concepts to acquire further insights into a subject or to apply various theories in different situations. "Eclecticism is defined as a type of methodology that makes use of the different language learning approaches instead of sticking to one standard approach" (A L Hamash, 1985:22).

According to Weidman (2001:2), "The Eclectic Approach has been widely accepted in English classrooms that many good teachers today use it proudly as a tag to describe to their teaching, wearing it almost like a badge of honour". Kumar (2013) supports the Eclectic Approach and declares, "The purpose of advocating eclectic method is to connect life experiences to the ideas presented in learning of the language. The types of learning activities teachers select are often directly related to their experiences in the real world." Brumfit (1984) emphasized that eclecticism was a right approach for language teaching and he further commented on language learning, "Language learning program should provide a balance of activities such as accuracy and fluency. Accuracy focuses on form and fluency on exchanging meaning, accomplishing tasks and reaching outcomes." As a result, many teaching specialists have endorsed the Eclectic Approach to language education, notably in ELT.

The Eclectic Approach in Language Teaching. As it includes various methods, approaches, and techniques and uses a specific method, approach, or technique that is appropriate for the classroom context, the Eclectic Approach is beneficial in teaching languages in a holistic manner. The Eclectic Approach is also used by language teachers in ELT, and it has proven to be effective in attaining objectives in EL classes. Let's look at how this Eclectic Approach is used by instructors to teach grammar, vocabulary, and language skills.

Grammar is regarded as the most crucial component of a language, because nothing can be communicated in a language without the use of grammar vocabulary. When grammatical rules are followed correctly, a language can be spoken or written correctly. Grammar is nothing more than a collection of rules for constructing sentences and organizing phrases and clauses in a reasonable and comprehensible manner. The Eclectic Approach can be used to teach grammar, particularly in the areas of combining and separating sentences, identifying pronouns and their antecedents, words and their synonyms, and prepositional phrases, with a focus on specific features of the language relevant to learners' contextual needs.

Vocabulary is one of the most important aspects of language, and it plays a significant part in all forms of communication, whether spoken or written. In reality, the quality of one's vocabulary clearly influences the level of one's language abilities. Teachers of English language pay close attention to vocabulary and encourage students to study vocabulary in a methodical manner while also understanding the context.

When teaching vocabulary, an English instructor follows three fundamental rules. To begin, he attempts to put the terminology into perspective for the kids. Second, he attempts to control the translation process, and third, he devises a system for pupils to predict or extract the meaning of words. By using the Eclectic Approach, the teachers of English language follow these guidelines in teaching vocabulary effectively. In the words of Horn by (1994:1425), "Vocabulary is total number of words that make up a language, list of words with their meanings, especially one which accompanies a text book in foreign language, vocabulary is also called lexicon, glossary or list of words. While stressing the importance of Vocabulary, Brown, (1994:365) says, "Vocabulary is seen in its role in contextualized, meaningful language." Here we can understand how important vocabulary is for a language.

Teachers use the Eclectic Approach to teach English grammar, which incorporates listening and speaking abilities. Teachers emphasize students' speaking skills during listening and speaking activities by teaching important grammatical aspects such as parts of speech, voice, word sequencing, concord, sentence comprehension, and sequential order of thought in speech, as well as the ability to interpret and make a critical evaluation.

ELT emphasizes discourse-based activities above sentence-based activities. Teachers may effectively teach reading skills in their English classes by using the Eclectic Approach. Students are separated into groups for reading activities, and each group is required to come up with a common response to the task. Students

here discuss their opinions about the context with one another and rewrite the phrases. Students are encouraged to work in groups to complete the reading activities in this discourse-based method.

Teachers and scholars have attempted to design a strategy that fits to the demands of modern English learners in light of the great expansion and rising interest in studying English writing. Writing instruction is founded on the concept of providing learners with knowledge about the syntax and structures of the language through a variety of tasks. Pluralism, in conjunction with the principle of eclecticism, allows teachers to choose instructional methods that align with unique learning requirements and empower students to communicate via their talents. According to Howard (2001) "the Eclectic Approach in teaching writing composition holds a particular fascination for learners. It enhances small group discussion and peer response in which students individually draft an assigned paper and then classmates respond, making suggestions for improvement." This is also known as collaborative pedagogy, and it is a component of the Eclectic Approach. If the social, creative, and cognitive components of language acquisition are correctly understood, teaching English writing may be productive and functional. It entails a number of different instructional methods. Only then can the fundamental purpose of writing instruction become a reality.

Advantages of Eclectic Approach.

Language learners are always looking for new ways to learn the language, something that is both innovative and exciting. Language teachers use a variety of methods, approaches, and tactics to

achieve this goal, ensuring that students learn the language in a comfortable and friendly environment. The following are the benefits of Eclectic Approach that have been carefully examined:

- This is a comprehensive method that encompasses a wide range of learning activities and provides learners with a break from boredom.
- Eclecticism entails a wide range of learning activities that are inspired by many underlying ideas.
- It creates a good learning environment in which the student-student relationship is improved.
- It is easier and more possible for the learners to understand the language of text with the context of culture.
- It's the ideal setting for extensive role-playing and "real-world" gaming activities.
- It combines the practice of listening, speaking, reading and writing into an organic whole.
- It suggests that, depending on the students' level, any method or strategy can be applied.
- The Eclectic Approach allows teachers to use any teaching approach that is appropriate for achieving the lesson's objectives.
- The Eclectic Approach simplifies the teaching of English by establishing realistic circumstances in the classroom.

The Eclectic Approach, while often regarded as the best approach in ELT and other topics, is not without its drawbacks. The Eclectic Approach has the following **disadvantages**:

- Teachers are discouraged from reflecting on their teaching when using the Eclectic Approach.
- This approach is heavily criticized since it provides no direction on the principles that may be utilized to choose and employ various approaches and strategies.
- Teachers find it difficult to choose the suitable component for a particular session, which causes some ambiguity.

Following extensive research and analysis, it has been determined that the Eclectic Approach offers more benefits than drawbacks. Therefore, teachers can use it to produce or obtain the desired results. Although language specialists have critiqued this method, it is commonly accepted and used by English teachers to create a dynamic environment in the classroom.

Conclusion. Language teachers ought to use a variety of ways since no single method, strategy, or technique is appropriate for all learners. Teachers should use a unified strategy to teach vocabulary, grammar, and language skills that incorporates all methods, approaches, and tactics. Here the Eclectic Approach accomplishes its goal and helps pupils to acquire the language in a systematic manner.

The Eclectic Approach makes grammar more successful, fun, and gratifying for students, allowing them to get a more intuitive knowledge of the English language and utilize it spontaneously. It has been extensively covered in this study work. As regards vocabulary, language teachers use specific methods, approaches, and tactics to teach vocabulary. Students may find a particular

method, strategy, or technique uninteresting and tedious at times. In this case, the Eclectic Approach is better since it combines all of the methods, approaches, and tactics to make vocabulary acquisition more enjoyable and fascinating.

It is critical for a teacher to teach each language skill in the context of a real-life event. When teachers use a single strategy or approach in a systematic fashion, pupils may become confused and make mistakes. While speaking and writing, learners may make mistakes in their phrases. Instructors must use a single, unified strategy to repair their faults and effectively advise their students. This approach encourages teachers to use all

available methods, approaches, and tactics. Because the Eclectic Approach has all of these advantages, language teachers may successfully use it in their classrooms to improve students' language abilities. As a result, it has been thoroughly examined in this work.

We have covered all of the key elements of the Eclectic Approach, as well as its benefits and drawbacks, as well as how to effectively use it in English classes, in this study article. Language instructors, educationalists, and researchers may still conduct creative Eclectic Approach study by gathering samples from diverse schools, colleges, and institutions throughout the world.

References:

1. Al-Hamash, I. Khalil & Younis Hamdi. (1985). *Principles and Techniques of Teaching English as a Second Language*. Baghdad: Al-Shaaab Press. pp. 22.
2. Brown, H. Douglas. (1994). *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Regents. pp. 365.
3. Brumfit, Christopher. (1984) *Communicative Methodology in Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
4. Gilliland, B. E. , James R. K., & Bowman, J.T. 1994. Response to the Lazarous and Beutler's Article "On Technical Eclecticism". *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 72, 544-555.
5. Hornby, A. S. (1995). *Oxford Learner's Dictionary, fifth edition*. Oxford: Oxford Group Limited. pp. 1425.
6. Howard, R. M. (2001). Collaborative Pedagogy. In G. Tate, A. Rupiper & K. Schick (Eds.), *A guide to composition pedagogy* (pp. 54-70). New York: Oxford University Press.
7. Kumar, C. P. (2013). *The Eclectic Method: Theory and Its Application to the Learning of English*. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(6):ISSN 2250-3553.
8. Weidman, A. (2001). *The Old and the New: Reconsidering Eclecticism in Language Teaching*. *Linguam*, 17(1):1-13. [Doi.org/10.5785/17-1-131](https://doi.org/10.5785/17-1-131).